

Holistic and forward-looking methodology for multi-criteria optimization of building energy renovation

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RESUME. Cette étude présente une approche novatrice d'optimisation multicritère des stratégies de rénovation, intégrant le confort thermique dans les évaluations économiques et environnementales. Grâce à des séries climatiques prospectives, les besoins de refroidissement et les gestes de rénovation associés sont particulièrement étudiés. L'analyse des fronts de Pareto sur l'étude de cas d'une maison individuelle révèle des compromis entre confort thermique, empreinte carbone et coût global. Elle met en lumière, pour ce cas particulier, la nécessité de rénover en même temps le système de chauffage et d'isoler les murs, tandis que la climatisation et le passage à une ventilation double flux sont facultatifs. L'intégration d'une année-type climatique future, sans canicule, aggrave l'inconfort thermique des stratégies de rénovation mais ne modifie pas le choix des stratégies optimales. Cette étude initiale sera prochainement complétée par l'ajout de nouvelles stratégies de rénovation, de facteurs d'émissions prospectifs ainsi que de séquences climatiques caniculaires.

MOTS-CLÉS : Rénovation, Optimisation multi-critères, Prospective

ABSTRACT. This study presents an innovative approach to multi-criteria optimization of renovation strategies, integrating thermal comfort into economic and environmental assessments. Thanks to prospective climate series, cooling needs and associated renovation actions are particularly studied. The analyses of the Pareto fronts on the case study of a single-family home reveal trade-offs between thermal comfort, carbon footprint and total cost. It highlights, in this case, the need to renovate the heating system and insulate the walls at the same time, while air conditioning and the switch to double flow ventilation are optional. The inclusion of a future climate model year, without a heat wave, aggravates the thermal discomfort of renovation strategies but does not change the choice of optimal strategies. This initial study will soon be supplemented by the addition of new renovation strategies, forward-looking emission factors and heat wave weather sequences.

KEYWORDS : Renovation, Multi-Criteria Optimization, Foresight

1. INTRODUCTION

In France, the building sector represents about 150 MtCO₂eq in life cycle, or 25% of the carbon footprint, and a third of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are due to construction products and equipment (Pellan et al. 2022). Given the decarbonization targets of the National Low Carbon Strategy (SNBC), the objective is to reduce emissions to 96 MtCO₂eq in 2030 and 16 MtCO₂eq in 2050 (« Réglementation environnementale RE2020 » 2020). The massification of the renovation of the building stock is obviously one of the major levers for achieving these objectives. Indeed, the various carbon neutrality scenarios set the target of 600,000 to 1 million efficient renovations in 2030, well

beyond what has been observed so far (ADEME 2022a). But to reduce the sector's life-cycle impacts, it is necessary to guard against the transfer of impacts between energy-related emissions and emissions related to building components. This is how LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) has been developed in the building sector, initially on new construction ((Polster et al. 1996; Kohler 1986) and then more recently for renovation (Vilches, Garcia-Martinez, and Sanchez-Montañes 2017).

In addition to these challenges of mitigating climate change, renovation must also meet the challenges of adaptation. With rising temperatures (IPCC 2023), the integration of summer comfort into the design and implementation of renovations is also essential. First studies underline that optimal renovations considering environmental and economic impacts may not be the best regarding the thermal comfort (Galimshina et al. 2021); (Mostavi, Asadi, et Boussaa 2017). Recently, thermal comfort has been integrated into the multi-criteria optimization of renovation strategies, but this is still in development (Mostafazadeh, Eirdmoussa, et Tavakolan 2023; Amini Toosi et al. 2020) ; (Mostavi, Asadi, et Boussaa 2017). However, thermal comfort is mainly studied through the measurement of thermal discomfort, which does not focus on health risk. The NF EN ISO 11399 standard recalls the difference between these two concepts.

This paper studies the selection of optimal renovation strategies according to 3 complementary criteria, following a Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) methodology. Particular attention is paid to the evolution of the need for cooling and thermal comfort, in a logic of global warming. This is why a cooling-related renovation gesture is proposed in the study.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology presented here aims to evaluate and identify optimized renovation solutions that can be applied to an existing building. It deals with three major issues involved in the life cycle of a renovated building: the carbon footprint of the renovation, the summer thermal comfort for the occupants and the overall cost associated with the renovation. The solutions studied concern changes to the thermal envelope and/or HVAC systems, without staggering over time. These 3 main subjects are detailed below.

2.1. LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT: THE CARBON FOOTPRINT

The choice of the LCA methodology specific to building renovation was made following the census work carried out by (CEREMA 2023) and is described precisely by (ADEME 2022b) This method only considers future impacts in the life cycle of the renovated building, with different assumptions depending on the type of component. A methodology similar to new buildings (« Réglementation environnementale RE2020 » 2020) is applied for new components, while only end-of-life impacts are taken into account for registered components. Regarding the preserved components, the impacts considered are the life in operation (depending on the remaining life in the renovated building), the end of life as well as the renewal during the reference study period. A reference study period of 50 years is chosen, in line with the RE2020 and reviews in the literature (Amini Toosi et al. 2020)

To quantify energy consumption, the use of a dynamic energy simulation is necessary. It aims at assessing the energy consumption by item (heating, domestic hot water, air conditioning, lighting, ventilation, and auxiliaries, etc.) and by energy vector (gas, electricity, wood, heating network, etc.). The Cometh-SED model is retained in this methodology (Silva et al. 2016).

The environmental data comes from the French INIES database (Inies, s. d.) which is a reference in the building sector. Whenever it is possible, collective data is preferred, followed by individual data and finally environmental data by default. The GWP100 midpoint indicator (kgCO₂eq) is used to calculate the carbon footprint. It is then reduced to the living area and to the year, to be in kgCO₂eq/m²/year. The carbon footprint is the only indicator currently evaluated in our LCA, as it is the most studied (Amini Toosi et al. 2020).

2.2. THERMAL COMFORT EVALUATION AND WEATHER CONDITIONS

Summer thermal comfort is assessed by studying the building's ability to limit overheating in the living rooms. In the methodology presented here, we focus on the study of thermal comfort in moderate thermal environments, in accordance with NF EN ISO 11399. The approach consists of measuring Degrees-Hours (DH, in °C.h) over a year of simulation, i.e. quantifying the duration and intensity of temperature thresholds exceeded. We establish a threshold based on operating temperature, which depends on adaptive comfort (Dear and Brager 1998) and is applied in the regulations for new construction (« Réglementation environnementale RE2020 » 2020).

Two climate series are used in this study, using the EURO-CORDEX database (Moss et al. 2010). The first is a typical year based on observations between 1981 and 2019, while the second is a forward-looking climate year over the period 2020-2058. This forecast is obtained by combining a Global Climate Model (GCM) with a Regional Climate Model (RCM), considering a Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) of 8.5, i.e. the pessimistic global warming scenario that can be considered as "business as usual" (Gobiet, Jacob, and Community 2012). Beforehand, depending on the location of the building studied, a bias-correction procedure (Kraiem, Alessandrini, and Rey 2020) was used by employing ERA5 observed data over the same period (1981-2019), followed by a Hermite cubic interpolation from 3 hours to 1 hour.

2.3. LIFE CYCLE COST: TOTAL COST

The life cycle cost analysis is used to estimate the total cost of the renovation. The objective is to evaluate the overall cost that accounts for the different costs operating over the life cycle of the renovated building (Elbeze 2018) As it stands, the total cost is calculated as the sum of the initial investment cost and the operating cost related to energy consumption. A discount rate of 3.2%, is considered as it is the reference rate for public investment set by (France Stratégie 2021). The initial investment cost is calculated using the Batiprix database (Batiprix 2024) which references the cost estimates for construction materials and the workforce in the building sector, for new construction or renovation. The data from 2022 were used.

The operating cost corresponds to the cost of the final energy consumed by the occupant over the reference study period (in this case 50 years). A forward-looking economic assessment is carried out here by integrating future modelling of annual energy prices. The reference values were taken in 2023 with the values issued by the SDES (SDES 2023) Then, an annual growth rate is applied based on the values established as part of the National Low Carbon Strategy in France (DGEC 2023). Since the modelling stops in 2050, we assume that prices remain constant between 2050 and 2073. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the price of the main energy sources, in constant 2023 euros. In this study, the evolution of energy prices is fixed and does not depend on the climate series chosen.

Figure 1 : Energy price trends according to the SNBC (AME scenario)

2.4. RENOVATION ACTIONS

A database has been assembled gathering representative building retrofit individual actions on the main renovation items: the insulation of walls, roof, and floor, the replacement of windows, the replacement of heating, ventilation, air conditioning and DHW (Domestic Hot Water) production systems. Each of the referenced renovation actions is associated with technical and physical characteristics, environmental data, and costs. The database makes it possible to compile packages of work that constitute the experimental design of the approach to evaluate and identify optimized solutions. Every renovation action is then linked to a dynamic model of the building's materiality, following a decomposition established by (Mailhac 2019), so that every adding and removal of components can be materialized.

2.5. SELECTION OF OPTIMAL RENOVATION STRATEGIES

An experimental design is then drawn up to evaluate different renovation strategies, depending on the building's technical constraints. To evaluate optimal solutions, we study the Pareto dominance relationship, which is the most famous and widespread approach (Deb 2001). Namely, solution x^* dominates solution x in the decision space if and only if:

$$\begin{cases} \forall i \in [1 \dots N], f_i(x^*) \leq f_i(x) \\ \exists k \in [1 \dots N], f_k(x^*) < f_k(x) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Pareto dominance is thus measured based on the 3 indicators selected: the carbon footprint, the total cost, and the degree-hours of thermal discomfort.

3. CASE STUDY

The methodology is applied on the retrofit project of a single-family residential building. The case study is described in the Table 1.

	Case study
Usage	Individual housing
Typology	T4, wall in solid concrete block
Year of construction	1975-1985
Department	33
Climatic zone	H2c
Ground floor area (m ²)	95
Number of storeys	0

Wall	25cm, no insulation
Roof	Attic Floor, 8cm glass wool (U=0.485 W/m ² .K)
Windows	Single-glazed windows in wood (U _w =4.7 W/m ² .K)
Ventilation	Self-adjusting mechanical ventilation (P=50W, f=1.1m ³ /h)
Heating	Electric radiators (P=1.2 kW)
Cooling	None
Domestic Hot Water	Individual electric hot water tank
Primary Energy Coefficient (kWh/m ² /year)	676.1

Table 1 : Case study

Each renovation strategy is composed by a set of renovation actions detailed in Table 2. 840 renovation strategies have then been evaluated, for all possible combinations.

Id	Heating (H)	Cooling (C)	Ventilation (V)	Wall (Wa)	Roof (R)	Windows (Wi)
1	Air/air heat pump (P=8 kW, SCOP=3.9)	Air/air heat pump (P = 3 kW, SEER = 8.24)	Dual-flow ventilation (P = 26.5 kW)	II (Internal Insulation) : wood fiber (U = 0.38 W/m ² .K)	II : biobased (U = 0.1 W/m ² .K)	Double-glazed windows in PVC (U _w = 1.4 W/m ² .K)
2	Pellet stove heater (P = 25kW)			II: glass wool (U = 0.27 W/m ² .K)	II : rock wool (U = 0.11 W/m ² .K)	
3	Gas boiler (P = 24 kW)			EI (External Insulation) : wood fiber (U = 0.35 W/m ² .K)		
4	Wood boiler (P= 27kW)			EI: glass wool (U=0.44 W/m ² .K)		
5				EI: wood fiber (U = 0.16 W/m ² .K)		
6				EI: glass wool (U = 0.16 W/m ² .K)		

Table 2 : Renovation gestures selected for the case study

Following the methodology described in Part 2, 2 climatic series adapted to Bordeaux are used. The first (*historic climate*) corresponds to a typical year following observations made in the city of Bordeaux between 1981 and 2019. The second (*future climate*) corresponds to a typical year between 2020 and 2058, combining the CNRS/CNRM Global Climate Model (CERFACS-CM5) and the Regional Climate Model of ETH (COSMO-CLM2). For example, the outdoor dry air temperature increases by an average of 0.9°C between the 2 series, and the maximum temperature increases by 1.6°C.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. HISTORIC CLIMATE

On the one hand, we analyze the Pareto fronts and the impacts for the historic climate series. Figure 2 synthesizes several messages. Range values for the 3 indicators are quite important and enable to classify renovation strategies. Among all the renovation strategies evaluated, 12 are on the 3D Pareto front, with 4 strategies being on the Cost/Carbon Pareto front. The whole set of 3D optimal strategies retrofit the heating system (wood boiler H4) and the wall (external biobased insulation Wa3), while half shifts to a dual-flow ventilation (V1). A quarter installs an air/air heat pump for cooling purposes. The existing building, because of a high and costly energy consumption (26 kgCO₂/m²/year, 35€/m²/year and 451°C.h), is one of the worst possible strategies.

Figure 2 : Impacts of renovation strategies (historic climate).

4.2. INFLUENCE OF THE CLIMATE SERIES

On the other hand, we analyze the influence of the climate series on the 3 indicators. *Figure 3* focuses on thermal discomfort and carbon footprint while *Figure 4* compares thermal discomfort and total cost.

First, these two figures enable to easily classify renovation strategies according to the induced thermal discomfort. If we consider the historic climate series, 4 groups can be made : 1/ installation of air conditioning (C1; DH = 0 °C.h), 2/ external insulation of the walls (Wa3,4,5,6; DH between 250 and 350 °C.h), 3/ no insulation of the walls (DH between 400 and 450 °C.h) and 4/ internal insulation of the walls (Wa1,2; DH between 480 and 550 °C.h).

Secondly, the comparison between historic and future climate series impacts results in different ways. Because of the average global warming, the thermal discomfort is increased when considering the future

climate : +100 to 200°C.h for the group 2 and +200 to 300 °C.h for groups 3 and 4. Total cost and carbon footprint, however, are only slightly modified. This can be explained by the assumptions made in the modelling. The future typical year only represents a trend increase in temperature and does not consider the frequency and intensity of any future heatwaves. This results in a reduction in heating requirements and a slight increase in cooling requirements, while average thermal discomfort, measured over the year, increases. The overall cost, as defined in 2.3, already considers prospective evolutions so it is not directly influenced by the choice of the climate series. Finally, out of the 12 optimal renovation strategies in a historic climate, 11 constitute the set of optimal renovations in a future climate. The renovation H4-C1-V1-Wa3-R1 is the strategy that is only optimal in a historic climate.

Figure 3 : Comparison between historic and future climate series considering thermal discomfort and carbon footprint.

Figure 4 : Comparison between historic and future climate series considering thermal discomfort and total cost.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this work allows a first evaluation of a new approach to multi-criteria optimization of renovation strategies. First, this methodology goes beyond the economic and environmental optimizations that may already exist, by integrating the essential notion of thermal comfort. This is reflected in the addition of a dedicated indicator, the thermal discomfort in degree-hours, but also in the modelling of renovation actions related to cooling. Air conditioning modelling is therefore a first step. This question of thermal comfort is further reinforced by the fact that prospective climatic sequences are considered in the methodology, including a warming of the outside temperature.

In addition, the coherence of the various simulation tools, from dynamic energy simulation to LCA and economic evaluation, makes it possible to bring a new perspective to the renovation strategies favored by the various stakeholders. The case study with an individual housing constructed in 1980 is a first example. Insulation from the inside reduces heat loss just as much as insulation from the outside, but the drop in inertia can be damaging to thermal comfort. Moreover, the analyses of the Pareto fronts highlight the different possible approaches : renovation of the heating system and exterior walls are necessary, but the installation of an air/air heat pump for cooling as well as a dual-flow ventilation are not mandatory. Besides, considering a typical year in a future climate increases thermal discomfort, but only marginally modifies the identification of 3D Pareto solutions.

Finally, we would like to point out that this article is a first evaluation of this methodology, and many developments are planned, to strengthen and consolidate these results. On the one hand, the number of renovation strategies needs to be significantly expanded, now that the method has been approved. Scenarios combining multiple energy systems and the renovation of the envelope, or the addition of heating networks must be integrated. A filtering of possible renovation strategies, depending on

technical constraints and the environment, is also planned. On the other hand, regarding indicators, greater attention needs to be paid to cost. The calculation of an overall cost, including the costs of repair, maintenance, and deconstruction, is in line with this idea. The indication of a carbon payback time for LCA is also envisaged. Regarding foresight, the objective is to extend it to LCA, by varying the emission factors of energy carriers, but also to energy simulation by modifying occupancy scenarios. Climate series incorporating severe heat waves are also being studied, to assess the health risk and no longer only thermal comfort.

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